

Defect Activity in Lead Halide Perovskites

*Silvia G. Motti, Daniele Meggiolaro, Samuele Martani, Roberto Sorrentino, Alex J. Barker,
Filippo De Angelis, Annamaria Petrozza*

Dr Silvia G. Motti, Roberto Sorrentino, Samuele Martani, Dr Alex J. Barker, Dr Annamaria
Petrozza

Center for Nano Science and Technology @PoliMi, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, via G.
Pascoli 70/3, 20133, Milan, Italy

E-mail: annamaria.petrozza@iit.it

Roberto Sorrentino, Samuele Martani

Dipartimento di Fisica, Politecnico di Milano, Piazza L. da Vinci, 32, 20133 Milan, Italy.

Dr Daniele Meggiolaro, Prof Filippo De Angelis

Department of Chemistry, Biology and Biotechnology, University of Perugia, Perugia, Italy.

Computational Laboratory for Hybrid/OrganicPhotovoltaics (CLHYO), CNR-ISTM, Via Elce
di Sotto 8, 06123, Perugia, Italy

CompuNet, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Via Morego 30, 16163 Genova, Italy.

‡ E-mail: filippo@thch.unipg.it

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The presence of various types of chemical interactions in metal halide perovskite semiconductors gives them a characteristic “soft” fluctuating structure, prone to a wide set of defects. Here we summarize our understanding of the nature of defects and their photochemistry, which leverages on the cooperative action of density functional theory investigations and accurate experimental design. Based on such knowledge we describe how defect activity determines the macroscopic properties of the material and related devices. Finally, we discuss the open questions which still need to be addressed in order to achieve an educated prediction of device operation, necessary to engineer reliable devices.

1. Introduction

Upon disclosure of the first reports on efficient solid state perovskite solar cells,^[1,2] one of the main surprises was the high open circuit voltage of such devices despite the active materials being solution processed. The reported long carrier lifetimes and diffusion lengths have directed a considerable amount of research towards investigating the nature of the carriers,^[3–6] and the role of electronic structure^[7–10] in their transport and dynamics. To complete the picture, researchers require an accurate understanding of the role played by defects in the photophysics of these materials,^[11–13] which by extension requires an understanding of the chemical nature and activity of those defects. Several studies indicate a significant probability for the formation of native defects in MAPbI₃, however these would mainly introduce shallow electronic trap states (i.e. states lying close to the band-edges, comparable to or less than the available thermal energy).^[10,14,15] This would explain the limited impact of defects on solar cell performance. Nevertheless, the presence of deep trap states is experimentally tangible.^[16] The photoluminescence quantum yield, for example, has a strong dependence on the photo-excitation density, as a result of a trap-filling process,^[11,13,17] which implies the presence of

fairly deep trap states. Trap states have also been detected within the perovskite band-gap by electrical measurements, with very low trap densities of about 10^{11} cm^{-3} reported for MAPbI₃ single crystals,^[18] but increasing up to 10^{18} cm^{-3} for polycrystalline thin films.^[11,19,20]

The main difficulty in understanding the role of defects in metal halide perovskites arises from the intrinsic soft nature of these materials.^[12,21] This results in a dynamic defect picture where the trap density is not fixed, as the various defect species that are associated with these electronic trap states may be created or destroyed in response to external stimuli.^[17,22–25]

Considering the established importance of defects in affecting perovskite-based device efficiency and temporal stability, a general understanding of defect properties and of possible remedying solutions is desirable.

Here we summarize our understanding of the nature of defects and their photo-chemistry in metal halide perovskite semiconductors, which leverages on the cooperative action of density functional theory investigations and accurate experimental design. Based on such knowledge we describe how defect activity determines the macroscopic properties of the material and related devices.

2. Defect chemistry and photophysics

To depict the defect activity in lead halide perovskites, the first step is to identify the nature and density of traps in the related MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃ perovskites, where the only chemical difference is the replacement of iodine by bromine. We resort here to state-of-the-art first principles simulations based on hybrid Density Functional Theory (DFT), including dispersion corrections and spin-orbit coupling, in order to obtain an accurate description of the energetics of the perovskite band-edges. We can thus calculate the defect formation energy (DFE) and thermodynamic ionization levels (TILs) associated with each defect species, allowing us to determine the relative abundance and trapping activity of those defects, respectively. We then experimentally probe the spectroscopic features of the identified species, and how the photo-

carrier dynamics and the response of the material to external stimuli are determined by their chemical nature.

2.1. Native Defects in MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃: Theoretical Predictions

The investigation of the nature and density of native defects in lead-halide perovskites can be accurately carried out by using DFT techniques in the supercell approach.^[26] To quantitatively estimate DFEs, however, DFT calculations should be performed by using hybrid functionals, such as HSE06 or PBE0,^[27,28] including spin-orbit coupling corrections. This approach is critical in order to obtain an accurate description of the energetics of the band-edges due to the dramatic impact of self-interaction errors in these systems.^[16,29]

Within the supercell approach, the DFEs are conventionally calculated by eq. (1):^[26]

$$DFE(X^q) = E(X^q) - E(perf) - \sum_i n_i \mu_i + q(E_F + V + \Delta V) + E^q \quad (1)$$

where $E(X^q)$ is the energy of the supercell with defect X in the charge state q , $E(perf)$ the energy of the perfect (non-defective) supercell, n and μ are, respectively, the number and the chemical potentials of the species added or subtracted to the non-defective system to form a defect; q is the charge of the defect. The last two terms of eq. (1), $q(E_F + V + \Delta V)$ and E^q , represent the energy due to the exchange of electrons with the Fermi level of the system, corrected for the electrostatic potential shift ΔV of the defective system induced by the defect and the long-range electrostatic interaction between the periodic defects images. The Fermi level is allowed to vary within the band-gap and is referenced to the valence band maximum (VBM) of the pristine crystal, i.e. $E_F=0$ at the top of the valence band. Based on eq. 1, the defect formation energy of a charged defect varies linearly across the Fermi level (i.e. band-gap of the material), with a slope fixed by the charge state q of the defect. The crossing points between DFE lines of different charge states define the thermodynamic ionization levels (TIL), i.e. the Fermi energies where DFEs of the same defect in different charged states are equal. These points correspond

to the oxidation-reduction potentials of that defect specie referred to the VBM of the material and assume a prominent role in the study of the photophysics of defects. The positions of TILs in the band-gap define whether the defect may act as a trap of photo-generated carriers. Specifically, based on the Shockley-Read-Hall theory of recombination,^[30] defects with TILs placed deep in the band gap-have an increased trapping activity on charges, leading to more pronounced losses in photo-efficiency.

In Figure 1 the DFEs calculated for various point defects in MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃ are reported, as calculated by simulating halide-medium conditions, corresponding to a 1:1 ratio of the PbX₂ and MAX (X=I, Br) precursors. By looking at the most stable defects, i.e. those with the lowest DFEs, one notices a similar defect chemistry in the two perovskites. In halide-medium conditions the most stable defects in both MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃ are methylammonium (MA) and halide interstitials, i.e. MA_i⁺ and I_i⁻ / Br_i⁻, which set the Fermi level at ~0.7 and ~0.8 eV above the VBM with calculated band-gaps of 1.58 and 2.24 eV for MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃, respectively, in close agreement to reported experimental band-gap values. Both perovskites thus have a tendency to grow (slightly) p-doped in equilibrium conditions. MA_i are stable only in the positive charged states within the Fermi level range spanning the perovskite band-gap, and only show a shallow (+/0) transition occurring close to the conduction band minimum (CBM, see Figure 2). In such defects, the cation occupies interstitial positions on the facets of the Pb-X₆ (X=I, Br) octahedra, with relatively low DFEs at the native Fermi level of 0.57 eV and 0.51 eV in MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃, respectively, and associated densities of ~10¹² cm⁻³ (recall that our data refer to an ideal single crystal in equilibrium with the precursor phases). At the native Fermi level negatively charged interstitial halides balance the overall charge, with comparable DFE and associated defect density as MA_i⁺. In the interstitial positions both iodide and bromide are weakly bonded with crystal lattice halides by forming dimers at distances > 3.80 and 3.50 Å respectively, coordinated by two Pb atoms in a double bridge configuration (see Figure 3.a-b). Notably, in the p-regions of the

diagrams, i.e. for Fermi energy close to the VBM, such negative halide interstitials are not stable and tend to be oxidized to the corresponding positive I_i^+ and Br_i^+ interstitials, characterized by formation of X_3^- trimers with inter-halide distances of 2.95 and 2.60 Å in MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃, respectively.^[16] I_i^+ shows a larger stability, i.e. a lower DFE, along the Fermi level compared to Br_i^+ , leading to a sizable defect density ($\sim 10^{10}$ cm⁻³) at the native Fermi level comparable with negative I_i^- . The higher DFE of Br_i^+ leads, on the other hand, to a negligible density of such defects in MAPbBr₃. The higher stability of positive iodine interstitials is mainly due to the lower electronegativity of iodine compared to bromine, in line with the higher stability of I_3^- compared to Br_3^- species.

Lead vacancies, V_{Pb} , also contribute to the defect chemistry of MAPbI₃, with a fairly low DFE at the native Fermi level. V_{Pb} is less stable in MAPbBr₃ than in MAPbI₃, due to the deeper VBM of the former. V_{Pb} is stable in the 2- charge state in MAPbI₃ with a DFE of 0.66 eV, comparable to I_i^- and MA_i^+ , thus showing a comparable defect density. Notably, these defect species are among the most stable defects in all conditions of growth of the perovskite, highlighting the tendency in these systems to release metallic lead. However, the high activation energy of V_{Pb}^{2-} migration compared to halide or MA defects suggests that formation of surface metallic Pb may occur only at high temperatures or under high energy irradiation.^[31] Similarly to MA and halide interstitials, in the p-doped regions of the diagrams the charged V_{Pb}^{2-} is not stable and it tends to form V_I^+ and I_i^+ , following the reaction $V_{Pb}^{2-} + 2h^+ = V_{Pb}^0 = V_{Pb}^{2-} + I_i^+ + V_I^+$.^[29] Oxidation of V_{Pb}^{2-} with 2 holes actually leads to oxidation of lattice halides, with formation of I_i^+ and an iodine vacancy. A close similarity thus exists between halide interstitials and lead vacancies, as both defects contribute under-coordinated iodine atoms.

Halide vacancies, i.e. V_I and V_{Br} , although present in lower densities than the above-mentioned defects, are always stable in the positive charge along the entire Fermi level in both MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃ and partially represent possible compensating defects of I_i^- in the Frenkel pair formation process.^[22] Formation of halide vacancies in the lattice may couple to

vacancies of the metal through the formation of Schottky defects, i.e. $V(\text{PbI}_2)$ and $V(\text{PbBr}_2)$. As discussed by Walsh et al., these defect couples show low formation energies and do not introduce electronic disorder in the perovskite^[14]. Energies of formation of 0.12 and 0.31 eV have been calculated by us for $V(\text{PbI}_2)$ and $V(\text{PbBr}_2)$, respectively, at the PBE level. Due to the low formation energies, these Schottky defects thus represent possible compensation pathways to the formation of lead vacancies in the system.

Other defects such as Pb_i^{2+} and V_{MA}^- exhibit high formation energies at the native Fermi level, and are therefore unlikely to play a significant role in the defect chemistry of these systems.

2.1.1. Charge traps and trapping dynamics

The analysis of the thermodynamic ionization levels diagram reported in Figure 2 highlights that, among defects, those introducing levels deep in the band-gaps of the perovskites are the halide interstitials I_i and Br_i , and lead vacancies. The latter show slightly shallower transitions compared to interstitials but an overall similar behavior, as outlined above.^[29] Positive halide interstitials, i.e. I_i^+ and Br_i^+ , can trap electrons through the (+/0) transition placed at 1.01 eV and 0.72 eV above the VBM, respectively. Upon trapping of the electron, one of the I-I and Br-Br bonds of the trimers breaks by forming the neutral interstitials in the form of I_2^- and Br_2^- molecular species, where halides are bonded at distances of 3.26 and 2.90 Å (see Figure 3.a-b). As depicted by the diagram in Figure 3.c-d, the large lattice relaxation involved in the electron trapping process leads to the formation of metastable neutral interstitials which can only decay non-radiatively with the occurrence of barriers to recombination. A barrier of 0.29 eV has been calculated by us in the MAPbI_3 perovskite at the hybrid SOC level^[29]. We have identified these barriers to recombination as a possible reason for the extremely long lifetimes of filled electron traps in these materials^[29].

On the other hand, negative interstitials can trap holes through the (0/-) transition placed at 0.30 and 0.12 eV above the VBM for iodine and bromine respectively. The trapping of holes to form the neutral X_2^- species induces a more limited lattice rearrangement compared to the first case and it is likely that trapped species decay radiatively, resulting in short lifetimes. Notably a small energy barrier to hole trapping at such defects was reported, possibly reducing the trapping activity of interstitial halides^[32]. Thus, while both negative and positive halide interstitials feature low formation energies and are active in trapping holes and electrons (respectively), the large lattice reorganization and resulting long timescales for electron trapping and recombination at positive interstitials implicates negative interstitials, or analogously lead vacancies, as the key defect species driving undesirable non-radiative recombination processes in both MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃.

2.2. Defect Photophysics: Experimental Evidence

In this section we summarize our experimental investigations on charge traps and trapping dynamics in polycrystalline thin films of lead halide perovskites, which are a consequence of the photochemistry of halide defects as predicted in the previous section.

In Figure 4.a we probe the absorption spectrum from MAPbBr₃ over a broad spectral range. The high band-gap of MAPbBr₃ (relative to MAPbI₃) conveniently places its spectral features in the more experimentally accessible visible-NIR spectrum, allowing us to detect the photophysical signatures of key defect activities. By combining absorbance data from a spectrophotometer (UV-Vis) and photothermal deflection spectroscopy (PDS), we are able to probe sub-bandgap absorption up to six orders of magnitude weaker than band-to-band absorption. Beyond the optical edge of the semiconductor two sub-bandgap bands can be detected, one in the visible range (SG-Vis) centered around 700 nm (1.77 eV) and one at longer wavelengths >800 nm (<1.55 eV) (SG-IR). External quantum efficiency (EQE) spectra

measured by C M. Sutter-Fella et al.^[33] revealed the presence of electrically active sub-bandgap states at 1.9 eV and 1.35 eV, corresponding well with the SG-Vis and SG-IR absorption bands. In Figure 4.b we also show the PL spectrum of the same material. Here, at wavelengths longer than the band-to-band radiative recombination feature, one can find two emissive bands centered around 700 nm (1.77 eV) and 1100 nm (1.12 eV), mirroring those found in absorption (see also Figure S2 for low temperature spectra). Note that the relative intensity of these PL features is not comparable as the measurements were taken using Si and InGaAs detectors in the Vis and NIR spectral regions, respectively, and are not accurately corrected for spectral response. These features are assigned to the radiative recombination of trapped carriers, based on the following observations: The relative intensity of both the SG-Vis and SG-IR emission are quenched as the photo-excitation density increases, while the band-edge emission efficiency increases, as expected in the presence of a trap filling process (Figure 4.c-d). The two sub-bandgap bands show different lifetimes, indicating that they originate from two different emissive species (Figure 4.e). In particular, the low energy band (SG-IR) has an extremely long lifetime (hundreds of nanoseconds), while the higher energy band (SG-Vis) has a lifetime that is slightly longer, but still comparable to the one probed at the optical edge of the semiconductor (tens of nanoseconds). In Figure 5.a we compare the band-to-band radiative recombination to the transient absorption dynamics probed at the band-edge of MAPbBr₃. Here, photo-excitation leads to the transfer of electrons from the VB to the CB, leaving behind holes. Due to state-filling close to the band-edges by the photo-excited species, and the resultant Pauli blocking, optical absorption is reduced at the associated photon energies. This induces a transient transparency at the energies corresponding to the band-edge of the excited sample, measured as a positive $\Delta T/T$ (normalized transmittance change) signal, and commonly indicated as a photo-bleach (PB). As this signal is proportional to the sum of densities of holes and electrons in the VB and CB respectively, it allows us to track not just radiative recombination (as in tr-PL), but also the

populations of carriers that follow non-radiative recombination pathways, such as via trap-assisted recombination. In the latter case, while a trapped carrier would not directly contribute to the PB, it would leave an unbalanced charge in the other band, thereby indirectly contributing to the PB. Indeed, the PB kinetics in Fig 5.a clearly show a fast initial decay, followed by a long-lived component revealing the presence of trapped carriers. In general, transient absorption and photoluminescence kinetics from a given sample should not match exactly (as their amplitudes scale differently with carrier density). However, it is clear in Fig 5.a. that the time scales of the fast and slow PB components correspond well to the decay of the band-to-band and the SG-IR emission respectively, leading us to attribute the SG-IR band in MAPbBr₃ to emission from trapped carrier recombination. We applied the same investigations to MAPbI₃ (with an optical band edge near 800 nm, or 1.6 eV). We have identified a broad emissive band centered around 1000 nm (1.2 eV), also identified in EQE spectra,^[33] that exhibits a short lifetime on the order of few ns.^[29] On the other hand, we have not been able to detect emission further in the IR. Nevertheless, the PB dynamics monitored through TA (Fig 5.b) reveal the presence of trapped carriers in MAPbI₃ that decay on μ s timescales, as in MAPbBr₃, indicating that similar physical pathways exist in the two materials, but that the trapped carriers are too weakly emissive, or too deeply trapped, to be directly observed in the spectral range under investigation.

So far, we have shown that polycrystalline thin films of lead halide perovskites exhibit two trap-assisted recombination pathways, in addition to the band-to-band radiative recombination. One is clearly emissive, closer to the optical edge of the semiconductor and with a recombination rate comparable or slightly slower than the band-to-band recombination rate, and the other with a recombination rate orders of magnitude lower. The theoretical predictions assign these pathways to the recombination of trapped holes and of trapped electrons with their free carrier counterparts, respectively. We have tested this assignment^[34] by investigating

perovskite thin films interfaced with selective charge extracting materials, namely Phenyl-C61-butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM) as an electron extracting layer and 2,2(7,7(-tetrakis-(N,N-dimethoxyphenylamine)9,9(-spirobifluorene))) (spiro-OMeTAD) as a hole extractor. We studied MAPbI₃ thin films, made from PbCl precursors and in presence of hypophosphorous acid (HPA) as an additive by measuring time resolved photocurrent from planar devices where pristine perovskite thin films were compared to films interfaced to selective extracting layers. Figure 6.a. shows an intensity dependence of the transient photocurrent in MAPbI₃ thin films. At times $t < 1 \mu\text{s}$, the decays become steeper for higher excitation densities as previously observed via photoluminescence spectroscopy when moving from monomolecular to bimolecular recombination regimes. Interestingly, we also observe an extremely slow component in the photoconductivity traces that makes up an increasingly large fraction of the decay as the excitation density is reduced. This component has not generally been observed in the transient photoluminescence, which means that, whichever mobile photo-excited species is still present on these long timescales, it has a very low radiative efficiency. On the other side, these dynamics mirror very well the long TA dynamics described above. Notably this slow component makes up less than 10% of the total decay upon high excitation (10^{17} cm^{-3}) but approximately 50% of the total decay upon low (10^{15} cm^{-3}) excitation. This is in agreement with a trap filling process, i.e. as the trap states are filled, the photogenerated carriers move from a trap mediated recombination path to the bimolecular band-to-band recombination. This trap filling effect is also visible as an increase in steady-state photocurrent (Figure S3). Importantly, with PCBM electron accepting layers the long tail is still observable. On the other hand, in the samples interfaced with the the hole acceptor spiro-OMeTAD this long component is quenched. This observation, combined with the lower steady-state photocurrent in the spiro-OMeTAD coated film (Figure S3), is consistent with rapid hole transfer to the spiro-OMeTAD, leaving electrons in the perovskite, which clearly do not contribute to any photocurrent on time scales longer than tens of ns. A similar behavior is observed monitoring the TA dynamics at the

semiconductor absorption onset in the ns- μ s time regime, as shown in Figure 6.c. This can be rationalized by assigning the long decay dynamics to the recombination of free photo-generated holes and long living trapped electrons. To generalize this finding, we have also performed new experiments on MAPbBr₃ thin films. In Figure 7.a, 7.b and 7.c we monitor the SG-IR emission when the perovskite is interfaced with an insulating PMMA thin layer, and with PCBM or spiro-OMeTAD molecules, respectively. While the SG-IR band is still observable in the presence of PMMA and PCBM, it is quenched in the presence of spiro-OMeTAD. At the same time, the spiro-OMeTAD sample also shows lower radiative efficiency (Figure S4). In agreement, the long living dynamics probed by transient absorption at the PB band of the semiconductor (Figure 7.d) reflect our interpretation of the steady-state PL. For the perovskite thin film interfaced with spiro-OMeTAD, free holes are efficiently extracted, preventing the recombination of trapped electrons, thus quenching both the SG-IR band and the long lived PB. On the other hand, when free electrons are extracted, those trapped can still recombine with the free holes remaining in the thin films, therefore the SG-IR band is still observable.

These experimental results confirm that in lead halide thin films, trapped electrons have an extremely long recombination time, consistent with the presence of an energy barrier as predicted by theoretical studies described in Section 2.1, while trapped holes rapidly recombine as a consequence of the characteristic photo-chemistry of halides.

2.3. Defect (Re)Activity

Above we summarized the nature of defects that are most likely to occur in MAPbBr₃ and MAPbI₃ and have a relevant impact on the charge carrier dynamics. In this section we discuss the consequences of their presence on the semiconductor behavior and on the related devices.

2.3.1. Nature of Defects and Defect Tolerance

To illustrate the effect of the peculiar halide photo-chemistry on the optoelectronic properties of perovskite semiconductors we simulated the photoluminescence quantum yield (PLQY) of the semiconductor using a system of rate equations which take into account two types of trap states (See Section 2 in SI for details). One has lower rates for trapping and trap-assisted recombination (“slow traps”, with rate constant $k_t = 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ for trapping and $R_t = 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ for recombination of trapped carriers) to represent electron trapping sites (N_{te}) in comparison with the second type (“fast traps”, with rate constants $k_t = 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ and $R_t = 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1}$) which simulate the hole trapping sites (N_{th}). The parameters used for simulating the PLQY were based on previous reports in literature^[11,13,34,35] and fits of experimental data (See Figure S1 in SI). Figure 8 shows the simulated PLQY trends as a function of the excitation density obtained for a fixed total trap density and different ratios of N_{te} and N_{th} , i.e. the density of one set of traps is dominant with respect to the other by one order of magnitude (10^{15} cm^{-3} versus 10^{14} cm^{-3}). First, we provide a qualitative analysis of the effect of trapping and recombination dynamics on the effective semiconductor radiative efficiency. The excitation source considered in the calculation was a short pulsed ($\sim 200 \text{ fs}$, shorter than the typical photo-excitation lifetime in perovskites) monochromatic light with 250 kHz repetition rate, i.e. one pulse every 4 μs . The dashed lines in Figure 8 are obtained considering in the rate equation a single excitation pulse, while the solid line shows what happens when we take into consideration the pile up due to 10 consecutive pulses. The first condition highlights the role of trapping rates, the later highlights the role of long living trapped carriers. From the single pulse calculations, it can be observed that the lower trapping rates at electron trapping sites result in a higher effective PLQY, when compared to the case in which hole traps are dominant, as the obvious consequence of a reduced trapping probability. Further enhancement of the PLQY can be observed when we consider the trap filling effects due to several sequential pulses. This effect is more pronounced in the electron trap-rich case, where the extremely long lifetimes of trapped electrons allow for a saturation of the sites, thus reducing

the effective trap density. Of course, this observation has direct implications on the open circuit voltage (V_{OC}) of solar cells. In Lejtens et al.,^[34] we simulated the expected open circuit in an ideal case, where the V_{OC} of the device (with a band-gap of 1.65 eV) is solely determined by the quasi-Fermi level splitting. For this purpose, the steady state carrier densities were estimated at one sun illumination to determine the degree of quasi-Fermi level splitting for electrons and holes and therefore the theoretical V_{OC} . Here the role of interfaces has been disregarded. The ideal case of a defect free semiconductor, where bimolecular recombination is dominant, is then compared to the case of fast trapping and fast trap mediated recombination for both the electrons and holes, and the case of long living trapped electrons. In the ideal case of pure bimolecular recombination the device should achieve a V_{OC} of 1.30 V. This estimate drops to 1.14 V with the introduction of short lived trap carriers, lower than that reported for state-of-the-art perovskite devices^[36]. However, in the case of long living trapped electrons, the estimated V_{OC} increases to 1.26 V – not far from recently reported values of V_{OC} as high as 1.24 V from perovskite devices with a band-gap of only 1.63 eV.^[37]

Table 1. Calculated V_{OC} for the case of filled traps (bimolecular recombination), short lived trapped carriers, and long lived trapped electrons. Here τ_e and τ_h are the monomolecular lifetimes for trapped electrons and holes, respectively. Adapted from ^[34].

	Theoretical V_{OC} (V)
Bimolecular recombination	1.30
$\tau_e = \tau_h = 100$ ns	1.14
$\tau_e = 100$ ns, $\tau_h = 10$ ms	1.26

In summary, the lower rates for the trapping and trap-assisted recombination processes associated with electron trapping defects results in less effective loss channels, explaining the impressive defect tolerance found in metal halide perovskite semiconductors.

2.3.2. Nature of Defects and response of the material to light soaking and air

One of the greatest challenges in perovskite research is the extreme sensitivity of the material to environmental factors such as atmosphere and light. It has often led to inconsistencies regarding observations reported in literature and of course represents an obstacle to reliable device implementation.

We have found that the material response is strongly related to the nature of defects. We have observed a quenching of PL intensity when the material is illuminated in inert atmosphere (vacuum, $<10^{-5}$ mbar), that results in a hysteresis of the relative PLQY when measured as a function of the excitation intensity,^[17] as shown for MAPbBr₃ in Figure 9a. Figures 9.b and 9.c show the PL spectra of MAPbBr₃ taken in the visible and near infrared spectral range respectively, both before and after prolonged light exposure. First of all we observe a quenching of the band-to-band emission, in agreement with the reduction in PL intensity monitored through the PLQY. Interestingly, while the SG-IR band is simultaneously quenched, the SG-Vis band increases in intensity. Having clarified the origin of SG-Vis and SG-IR band in Section 2.2, we show that prolonged illumination under inert environment (approximately 40 minutes under constant illumination of a 250 kHz pulsed laser, at excitation densities around 10^{16} cm⁻³, in vacuum) results in an increased density of hole traps, which represent a more effective trap-assisted recombination center than the long living electron traps associated with SG-IR.

On the other hand, when the material is exposed to air (whether humid or dry), the opposite effects are observed. Figure 10.a compares the relative PLQY of MAPbBr₃ taken under high vacuum or in ambient atmosphere. The exposure to air results in higher PL efficiency and reduced hysteresis, which we and other groups have assigned to the passivation of defects by oxygen.^[17,25,38,39] The PL spectra after air exposure (Figure 10.b and 10.c) show decreased intensity of the SG-Vis band and increased intensity of the SG-IR band. This demonstrates that oxygen molecules interact with hole trapping defects, deactivating these efficient trap-assisted recombination centers.^[24] Importantly, their deactivation happens concomitantly with the enhancement of the SG-IR band. Here two possible scenarios are open. Oxygen effectively deactivates deep hole traps associated with iodide interstitials by forming moderately stable oxidized products (i.e. hypoiodite, iodite, iodate) which induce shallow hole trap states within the band-gap.^[24] The small energy gain associated with trap passivation is in agreement with the reversibility of the process. In this situation, the total density of trap states is reduced and electron trap states, which have a lower trapping rate, become dominant. Another possible mechanism, which somehow parallels the previous one, is the oxidation of Br⁻_i/I⁻_i to Br⁺_i/I⁺_i with the consequent partial inactivation of hole traps.^[24] A common aspect of both mechanisms is the conversion of hole traps into kinetically inactive electron traps, which may take place under mild oxidizing conditions, explaining the enhancement in band-to-band PL intensity.

It has been often observed an initial, slow, growth in photoluminescence also in presence of humid air..^[17,40] This effect has been suggested to result from a temporary hydration of the surface, which radically changes its structure, and eventually lead to irreversible degradation of the perovskite.^[41-43] Along with such process, despite the fact that, in contrast to oxygen, water is not expected to undergo chemical reactions with native traps, it may still contribute to passivate undercoordinated surface lead atoms by exploiting similar interactions than we have suggested about the interaction

between the perovskite surface and a thin layer of polyethyleneoxide (PEO), i.e. by setting up Pb-O chemical bonds^[46]. The deposition of interlayers is one strategy for protecting perovskite layers against atmosphere related degradation improve device stability.^[44,45] Moisture resistance can be improved with deposition of hydrophobic layers, however, poor wettability of hydrophobic compounds over the perovskite surface usually results in poor coverage. We have demonstrated the application of PEO, a hydrophilic polymer, as an interlayer for perovskite photovoltaic devices.^[46] PEO can be deposited as homogeneous, pinhole-free thin interlayers that do not hinder charge extraction. In addition to protecting the perovskite layers from moisture degradation, the PEO molecules, as described above, can passivate defects by binding to under-coordinated surface Pb.^[46] While under-coordinated Pb is associated with shallow trap states (which are not expected to be very detrimental for charge-carrier dynamics) it plays an important role in degradation mechanisms.^[43,47] Surface passivation is therefore key to control defect activity in perovskite layers and improve the semiconductor performance and stability.

3. Conclusions and Perspectives

With this work we have reported how the performance of lead halide semiconductors can be affected by their defect chemistry. Tress et al recently showed how the extraordinary development of power conversion efficiencies achieved in perovskite photovoltaics in the last years has been mainly driven by an improvement in the device open circuit voltage.^[36] In the first instance, the advances in research towards devices with enhanced V_{OC} have been driven by transformations in the thin film morphology and composition. Here we show that the thin film optimization comes along with changes in the associated defect chemistry, whose fingerprints have been described in this report. Early records of photoluminescence and transient absorption data were characterized by shorter carrier lifetimes and sub-bandgap bleaching features, evidencing a predominance of hole trapping defects.^[48,49] Recently, thin

film characterizations reveal a predominance of electron traps,^[29,34] in agreement with the impressive defect tolerance of lead halide semiconductors. Given the identification of such defects, a full set of open questions remains to be addressed. First of all, we need to understand how one can experimentally control the density of native defects by engineering the chemical composition and thin film processing. In this regard, parallel studies on 2D lead-halide perovskites may be instructive. Unfortunately, there is still not full comprehension of the origin of sub-bandgap states in any of the 2D perovskites, and the strongly excitonic nature of the primary photoexcitation with respect to 3D semiconductors will lead to different trapping and detrapping processes. There are good indications that the formation energy of such defects depends on the structural properties of the inorganic crystalline unit, and can be dramatically manipulated by engineering the chemical composition of the crystal. Some of us have shown that structural distortions of the perovskite lattice can determine the defectivity of the material by modulating the formation energies of color centers.^[50] Such color centers are identified as halide interstitials, inducing deep charge trap states within the band gap.^[50,51] Preliminary studies in our laboratories suggest a modulation of the defect activity in multi-cation compositions, though a rationalization of the processes is still missing systematic structural studies.

Interestingly, different surface passivation strategies have been presented in literature.^[48,52–56]

To a first approximation they are based on different types of molecular interactions.

Nevertheless, most of them, to varying extents, have some effect on the PLQY of the thin film and/or V_{OC} of the solar cell, as well as on the stability of the device. In this regard, future work must endeavor to unify all of these reports. For example it would be important to experimentally verify whether the chemistry of defects discussed so far can be extended from the bulk to the surface, or whether unique defects exist on the surface and, if so, how the (photo)chemistry of such surface defects can also affect the bulk properties of the semiconductor. Understanding and controlling the evolution of these bulk and surface defects

in response to external stimuli also remains a great challenge. We have shown that under light soaking, the density of hole trapping states increases. These same states are deactivated in presence of molecular oxygen. This clearly suggests that device stability under external stimuli is closely related to the chemistry of defects, demanding further clarification of the mechanisms behind such phenomena, given the apparent discrepancies so far reported in literature.^[57,58]

In summary, we have compiled an extensive collection of computational studies and experimental results that provide a comprehensive understanding of defect activity in lead halide semiconductors. We have identified the most predominant point defects in MAPbBr₃ and MAPbI₃ and found that the low trapping and trap-assisted recombination rates associated with electron trapping sites make these a less efficient loss channel when compared to hole trapping defects such as halide interstitials, and that the predominance of long-lived electron traps can contribute to enhance radiative efficiency and solar cell V_{oc}. The interplay between defect chemistry and semiconductor performance sheds light on the factors at play during the material optimization process over the past several years of research. Moreover, it also opens the possibility of developing intelligent fabrication methods and further enhancing performance and stability of these materials in the future.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Figure 1. Defect formation energies of a) MAPbI₃ and b) MAPbBr₃ calculated in halide medium conditions by using the HSE06 functional ($\alpha=0.43$) by including spin orbit coupling and a posteriori dispersion corrections. (a) has been adapted with permission from reference [29].

Figure 2. Thermodynamic ionization levels of most stable defects in MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃ calculated at the HSE06-SOC ($\alpha=0.43$) level by including spin-orbit coupling and dispersions corrections. The values for MAPbI₃ have been adapted with permission from reference [29].

Figure 3. Equilibrium configurations of a) iodine and b) bromine interstitials in their different charged states (Cyan: Lead; Purple : Iodine; Red: Bromine; Yellow: Iodine / Bromine atoms forming molecular defect species X_3^- , X_2^-). Configuration coordinate diagrams representing the relative energies of c) iodine and d) bromine interstitials vs the root mean square displacement of the three halides in the defect sites. Curves are aligned in order to simulate emission from the neutral trapped interstitial in all cases. (a) and (c) have been adapted with permission from reference [29].

Figure 4. a) Absorption spectrum and b) PL spectrum of MAPbBr₃; relative PLQY of MAPbBr₃ at the band-edge (530 nm, dark blue) compared to the subgap emission (red) at c) 700 nm (SG-Vis) and d) 1000 nm (SG-IR); e) PL decays of MAPbBr₃ at the band-edge

(530 nm, dark blue), SG-Vis (750 nm, light blue) and SG-IR (1000 nm, red). (c) has been adapted with permission from reference [17].

Figure 5. a) Transient absorption dynamics (dark blue) of a MAPbBr_3 thin film probed at the band-edge (525 nm), overlapped with the PL dynamics at the band-edge (530 nm, light blue) and at 1000 nm (red); b) Transient absorption dynamics (dark blue) of a MAPbI_3 thin film probed at the band-edge (770 nm), overlapped with the PL dynamics at the band-edge (780 nm, light blue). (a) has been adapted with permission from reference [29].

Figure 6. a) Transient photocurrent of MAPbI₃ films coated with PMMA at increasing excitation densities; b) Transient photocurrent of MAPbI₃ films coated with PMMA (dark blue) or Spiro (light blue), device architecture is illustrated in the inset; c) Transient absorption dynamics at the band-edge (770 nm) of MAPbI₃ coated with PMMA, Spiro or PCBM. Adapted with permission from reference [34].

Figure 7. PL spectra of MAPbBr₃ coated with a) PMMA, b) Spiro-OMeTAD and c) PCBM; d) Transient absorption dynamics at the band-edge (525nm) of MAPbBr₃ coated with PMMA (dark blue), Spiro-OMeTAD (light blue) and PCBM (red); e) Band diagram illustrating the band alignment and charge transfer between the perovskite layer and PCBM or Spirospirometad.

Figure 8. Simulated PLQY for $N_{te} > N_{th}$ (dark blue) and $N_{te} < N_{th}$ (red), where N_{te} is the density of electron traps and N_{th} the density of hole traps. Dashed lines are obtained from the calculation of a single excitation pulse, while the solid lines are obtained after a 10 pulse accumulation.

Figure 9. a) Relative PLQY curves of a MAPbBr₃ thin film taken in vacuum with increasing (solid lines) or decreasing (dashed lines) excitation densities; PL spectra of MAPbBr₃ thin films taken with b) a detector sensitive to visible light and c) an infrared sensitive detector, before and after prolonged illumination (approximately 40 minutes, 250 kHz, at excitation density around 10^{16} cm^{-3}). (a) and (b) have been adapted with permission from reference [17].

Figure 10. a) Relative PLQY curves of a MAPbBr₃ thin film taken in vacuum (blue) and air (red) with increasing (solid lines) or decreasing (dashed lines) excitation densities; PL spectra of MAPbBr₃ thin films taken with b) a detector sensitive to visible light and c) an infrared sensitive detector, before and after dry air exposure. (a) and (b) have been adapted with permission from reference [17].

Supporting Information

Defect Activity in Metal Halide Perovskites

Silvia Motti, Daniele Meggiolaro, Samuele Martani, Roberto Sorentino, Alex Barker, Filippo De Angelis, Annamaria Petrozza

1. Computational details

Defects calculations have been performed in the 2x2x1 tetragonal supercells of MAPbI₃ and MAPbBr₃ by fixing cell parameters to the experimental values for both phases, i.e. a=b=8.849 Å, c = 12.642 Å for MAPbI₃; a=b=8.345, c = 11.802 Å for MAPbBr₃.^[1] Defects structures have been optimized by using the PBE functional^[2] and ultrasoft pseudopotentials with a cutoff on the wavefunctions of 40 Ryd (320 Ryd on the charge density) and 1x1x2 k-point grids in the Brillouin zone (BZ). Defects formation energies have been calculated at the

hybrid level by using the HSE06 functional ($\alpha=0.43$)^[3] by including spin-orbit corrections and dispersions interactions a posteriori within the DFT-D3 scheme.^[4] Single point hybrid calculations have been performed at the calculated PBE structures by using norm conserving pseudopotentials and a cutoff energy on the wavefunctions of 40 Ryd and 1x1x2 k-points in the BZ. All calculations have been carried out by using the Quantum Espresso package.^[5]

Defects formation energies and thermodynamic ionization levels have been calculated following the approach reported in ^[6]. Chemical potentials have been set by imposing thermodynamic equilibrium between perovskites and the relative lead precursors, i.e.

$$1) \mu(\text{MAPbI}_3) = \mu(\text{MA}) + \mu(\text{Pb}) + 3\mu(\text{I}), \quad \mu(\text{Pb}) + 2\mu(\text{I}) = \mu(\text{PbI}_2)$$

$$2) \mu(\text{MAPbBr}_3) = \mu(\text{MA}) + \mu(\text{Pb}) + 3\mu(\text{Br}), \quad \mu(\text{Pb}) + 2\mu(\text{Br}) = \mu(\text{PbBr}_2)$$

Halides medium conditions have been modelled by using intermediate chemical potentials between halide-rich and halide-poor conditions. For halide rich conditions I and Br chemical potentials have been fixed to the values of the respective gas molecules, i.e. $\mu(\text{I}) = \frac{1}{2} \mu(\text{I}_2 \text{ gas})$ and $\mu(\text{Br}) = \frac{1}{2} \mu(\text{Br}_2 \text{ gas})$, while in halide poor conditions the chemical potentials of lead has been set to the metallic bulk Pb. Defects formation energies have been corrected by including potential alignment and Makov-Payne corrections (ionic dielectric constants $\epsilon=24.0$ and $\epsilon=20.0$ for MAPbI_3 and MAPbBr_3 , respectively).^[7]

2. Simulation of PLQY

The excited state dynamics of perovskite semiconductors can be described by a system of rate equations such as described in ^[8], where the evolution of populations of free electrons and holes ($n_{e,p}$) is calculated by taking into account the photogeneration rate (G), the radiative bimolecular recombination (with rate constant β_{rad}), the Shockley-Read-Hall recombination via trap states and third order non-radiative recombination (Auger-like processes, with rate constant γ).

The PLQY is obtained as:

$$PLQY = \frac{n_{PL}}{n} = \frac{\beta_{rad} n_e n_h}{n}$$

Where n_{PL} is the number of emitted photons and n is the number of photons absorbed.

Considering only one type of traps is generally a good approximation that shows good agreement with experimental data, since one type is usually dominant, and under constant illumination there is a slow population filling in these states. For having a better visualization of the effect of the distinct rates for different types of traps, we have adapted the model to distinguish between electron and hole traps, using the following system of rate equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dn_e}{dt} &= G - \beta_{rad} n_e n_h - k_{te} n_e (N_{te} - n_{te}) - R_{th} n_e n_{th} - \gamma n_e n_h^2 \\ \frac{dn_h}{dt} &= G - \beta_{rad} n_e n_h - k_{th} n_h (N_{th} - n_{th}) - R_{te} n_h n_{te} - \gamma n_e n_h^2 + G_{up} n_{th} \\ \frac{dn_{te}}{dt} &= k_{te} n_e (N_{te} - n_{te}) - R_{te} n_h n_{te} \\ \frac{dn_{th}}{dt} &= k_{th} n_h (N_{th} - n_{th}) - R_{th} n_e n_{th} - G_{up} n_{th} \end{aligned}$$

where N_{te} is the density of electron traps and N_{th} is the density of hole traps. n_{te} and n_{th} are the density of trapped electron and holes, k_{te} and k_{th} are the trapping rates and R_{te} and R_{th} are the rates of recombination of a trapped carrier with its counterpart.

It is considered that release of a trapped carrier only occurs when it recombines with a free carrier of opposite charge, considering this is more likely to occur than thermal activation of the trapped carrier back to the CB or VB. This means that, when including the two types of traps, part of the carriers will be permanently trapped without a recombination channel available. To circumvent that, it was considered an additional term for a trapped carrier to be released as a free carrier, with a rate G_{up} . Based on the theoretical predictions presented in Section 2.1 of the main text, electron trapping is associated with a lattice distortion, therefore one expects lower rates for electron trapping and detrapping compared to holes. For the sake

of simplification of the model, it is considered that due to the lower energy barriers for detrapping, only holes have a significant rate of release as a free carrier (G_{up}).

The parameters used for obtaining the curves in Figure 8 of the main text are presented below:

$$\begin{aligned}\beta_{rad} &= 1e-9 \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1} \\ k_{te} &= 1e-10 \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1} \\ R_{te} &= 1e-12 \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1} \\ k_{th} &= 5e-9 \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1} \\ R_{th} &= 1e-9 \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1} \\ G_{up} &= 1e-12 \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1} \\ \gamma &= 1e-26 \text{ cm}^3\text{s}^{-1}\end{aligned}$$

3. Sample preparation

Lead(II) bromide (PbBr_2 , $\geq 98\%$), N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, anhydrous, 99.8%), Chlorobenzene (anhydrous, 99.8%), and dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, anhydrous, $\geq 99.9\%$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich; methylammonium bromide (MABr) and methylammonium iodide (MAI) were purchased from Dyesol; and lead (II) iodide (PbI_2 , 99.9985%, CAS No. 10101-63-0) was purchased from Alfa Aesar. All chemicals were used without any further purification. Glass substrates were cleaned in acetone and isopropyl alcohol (IPA) for 10 minutes by sonication. The cleaned glass substrates were treated with Oxygen plasma for 10 minutes before any further deposition.

MAPbBr₃ thin films. These films could be fabricated by an adapted Nanocrystal-Pinning technique [Ref. Cho H. et al., Science (2015), 350-6265, 1222-5]. In this case, two steps of

spin-coating speed were used (500 rpm for 7 seconds, 3000 rpm 90 seconds). After spin-speed acceleration, a solution of MABr and PbBr₂ (molar ratio 1.05:1) in DMSO was spin-coated onto the clean glass substrate. After 60 seconds, the pinning occurred by dropping 300 μ l of chlorobenzene on the spinning sample. The samples were then baked at 90°C for 10 minutes.

MAPbI₃ thin films. These films were fabricated by quenching a precursor solution with an antisolvent during spin coating [M. Xiao et al., *Angewandte Chemie* vol. 126, p10056 (2014)], in a nitrogen filled glovebox. A 1.45 M precursor solution of PbI₂:MAI:DMSO in a molar ratio of 1:1:1 was prepared in DMF. This solution was spin coated onto the glass substrate at 4000 rpm, with an acceleration of 4000 rpm/s, for 15 s. After 6 s toluene, an antisolvent to the precursor solution, was dropped onto spinning sample by pipette. The samples were then annealed at 100°C for 10 minutes.

Thin films passivation. PCBM dissolved in chlorobenzene with a concentration of 20 mg/mL was spin coated with an acceleration of 2000 rpm/s for 45 s. PMMA dissolved in chlorobenzene with a concentration of 10 mg/mL was spin coated with an acceleration of 2000 rpm/s for 45 s. Spiro-OMeTAD solution is prepared by dissolving in 1 mL of chlorobenzene 75 mg of Spiro-OMeTAD and mixed with 30 μ L 4-tert- butylpyridine and 20 μ L taken from a stock solution of 520 mg/mL of Li-TFSI in acetonitrile. The solution was spin coated with an acceleration of 2000 rpm/s for 45 s.

4. Steady-state Photoluminescence

For MAPbBr₃ films, the excitation was provided either by a continuous wave diode laser (Oxxius laserboxx, 405 nm) or by a second harmonic of a Q-switched Ti:Sapphire based regenerative amplifier (Coherent RegA 9000) operating at 250KHz (400 nm, \sim 100 fs duration). The PL was collected in reflection geometry, perpendicular to the excitation line. Visible range spectra were acquired with a fiber coupled to a spectrometer (Ocean Optics

Maya Pro 2000) and near-infrared range spectra were acquired with a spectrometer coupled to an InGaAs based N₂ cooled photomultiplier.

For relative PLQY measurements, the integrated PL was measured at varying excitation intensities and plotted as:

$$\text{Relative PLQY} = \text{PL}/I_{\text{pump}}$$

Measurements were performed in vacuum under active pumping and pressure below 10⁻⁵ mbar.

5. Time-resolved Photoluminescence

The thin film samples were mounted in a chamber in vacuum (under 10⁻⁵ mbar). PL was collected in reflection geometry, perpendicular to the excitation line. Samples were excited from both sides of the sample (glass substrate or sample film), without any relevant difference between them.

Time-resolved PL measurements on MAPbBr₃ and MAPbI₃ films were performed using a Time Correlated Single Photon Counting setup. For MAPbI₃ measurements, the output of an unamplified tunable Ti:Sapphire laser (Coherent Chameleon Ultra II, temporal and spectral bandwidths of ~140 fs and ~5 nm, respectively) was tuned for central wavelengths of 700 nm. The measurements were performed with excitation at 2 MHz, obtained using an acousto-optical modulating pulse picker (APE Pulse Select). For MAPbBr₃ the laser source was a Q-switched Ti:Sapphire based regenerative amplifier (Coherent RegA 9000) operating at 250KHz seeded by a mode-locked Ti:Sapphire oscillator (Coherent Micra-18) operating at 80 MHz. Pulses of ~100fs duration of the second harmonic at 400 nm were obtained by focusing on a BBO crystal and directed to the sample.

The PL was collected and focused onto a spectrometer coupled to a N₂ cooled photomultiplier.

6. Transient Absorption Spectroscopy

Thin film samples were mounted in a chamber in vacuum (under 10^{-5} mbar). Transient absorption signal was collected in transmission geometry. An amplified Ti:sapphire laser (Quantronix Integra-C) generates pulses of ~ 100 fs centered at 800 nm. A broadband white light probe is generated by focusing the pulses into a thin sapphire plate. Long delay range can be achieved with pump light provided by a Q-switched Nd:YVO₄ laser (Innolas Picolo) which is electronically triggered and synchronised to the Ti:sapphire laser via an electronic delay. Including jitter, and the system has a combined time resolution and jitter of approximately 700 ps. After interaction with the sample, a home-built prism spectrometer disperses the probe light on to a fast CCD array, enabling broadband shot-to-shot detection. The excitation wavelength used was 532 nm (obtained by SHG of the fundamental output of the Nd:YVO₄ laser) for MAPbI₃ samples and 355 nm (obtained by Third Harmonic Generation) for MAPbBr₃ samples.

7. PDS

PDS is an ultrasensitive absorption measurement technique that detects heating of the sample due to the nonradiative relaxation of absorbed light and is insensitive to reflection and scattering.

The sample is placed in a cuvette filled with a transparent fluid (Tetradecafluorohexane) that has a great index of refraction gradient over temperature, so that, when the sample absorbs a monochromatic excitation light, it can relax the photo-generated heat into the portion of the fluid that surrounds its surface and change the refractive index of this small fluid volume. If we align a laser beam (HeNe) parallel and in close proximity to the sample's surface, we can measure the laser's deflection caused by the fluid's refractive index change. By doing this we can associate a deflection value (proportional to the absorption coefficient) for each excitation wavelength, and hence retrieve the absorption spectrum. The excitation is provided by a supercontinuum white laser filtered by a monochromator and modulated by an optical chopper (lock-in detection). The laser provides a higher power and better focusing than high power lamps.

Supporting Figures

Figure S1. Transient Absorption at the band edge of a MAPbBr₃ film (525nm) and a fit of the hole dynamics resulting from the rate equation model when considering only electron traps.

Figure S2. Temperature dependence of PL spectrum of a uncoated MAPbBr₃ film where the SG-Vis emission can be observed.

Figure S3. Photocurrent as a function of excitation density measured from MAPbI₃ in planar configuration (inset shows the device architecture) coated with PMMA, Spiro-OMeTAD or PCBM. Data reproduced from Leijtens et al.^[9]

Figure S4. Relative PLQY at the band-edge (530 nm) as a function of the excitation intensity of MAPbBr₃ films coated with PMMA, Spiro-OMeTAD or PCBM.

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